

Societal & Political Engagement
of Young People in Environmental Issues

D7.5: 2nd Report on Dissemination Activities

WP7 – Dissemination

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1 Executive summary

The purpose of this deliverable is to report the dissemination activities carried out during the second year of the STEP project implementation, i.e. June 2016 – May 2017. In particular, the objectives and expected results of the STEP project are briefly presented (Chapter 2), while the dissemination tools and the dissemination activities performed by partners until M24 (May 2017) are presented in Chapters 4 and 5. Chapter 6 is dedicated to the pilot partners' dissemination activities, and finally, the dissemination impact indicators are presented in Chapter 7.

The major dissemination achievements of the STEP consortium for this year are the following:

- The dissemination of the STEP project has been efficiently implemented through a number of online and offline activities.
- Most of the Dissemination Impact Indicators, initially set, have been achieved, since the project partners have attended/ organised several events in which STEP was presented.
- STEP has been presented to a number of local authorities and most of them found it very attractive and were interested in using it. Eventually, an additional pilot, which was not initially foreseen by the DoA joined the STEP pilots. This pilot will be implemented by the Municipality of Thessaloniki, which is located in Greece.

2 Dissemination objectives and expected results

As defined in the deliverable D7.7-2nd Dissemination Plan, the main objectives of the STEP dissemination activities are to:

- Raise awareness about the STEP project among youth throughout Europe. Achieve diversity and inclusiveness by involving a demographically balanced group of young people
- Raise awareness of local, regional and national policy makers and public bodies, especially regarding decision-making on environmental issues
- Maximise participation in operations offered by the developed platform / mobile app through the project by drawing the attention of young people using targeted communication means
- Ensure efficient communication and understanding regarding the project, obtain support and encourage participation of all stakeholders, as well as the general public in disseminating information and exploiting results
- Establish formal and informal networks and strengthen and valorise existing ones, for the purpose of exchanging ideas and practices, in order to develop a sense of community by participating in decision making in the fields of the environment and sustainable development and the public sphere in general

During the first eighteen months of project implementation, the main focus of the STEP dissemination strategy was to communicate and disseminate the activities of the STEP project, shaping an identity for the project and paving the way for the next phase, when the platform is ready and the consortium engages users in pilot areas. In month nineteen, when the internal testing period of the platform started, the pilot partners launched preparations for local dissemination activities, aiming at presenting the STEP platform in pilot

areas. The rest of the consortium supported the general dissemination of the STEP project. The ultimate goal is to ensure the STEP platform is used by a significant number of local authorities and young people.

These are the results expected from STEP dissemination activities:

- Raising awareness about project activities, informing target audiences and the general public about the existence of the STEP solution.
- Informing target groups about potential benefits from the use of the STEP platform.
- Achieving active participation of target groups in the project, e.g. via their attendance at project events and promotional activities.
- Attracting potential future stakeholders and ensuring maximum impact of the project.
- Stimulating the participation of experts in the STEP External Expert Advisory Board and increasing the members of the STEP Network of Interest.

3 STEP Dissemination tools

The following sections provide an insight in the performance of STEP's dissemination tools that have been prepared for the promotion of the project. Additionally, it presents the new promotional material, which was created after June 2016.

3.1 STEP website

[STEP's website](http://www.step4youth.eu) is on air since M3. It is a user- friendly, well- designed and easily accessible website, available at www.step4youth.eu, that was designed taking into account specific provisions and requirements related to the obligations of the EU, gender issues and target groups/stakeholders.

Figure 1: STEP website.

The STEP website consists of the public and private section. The public section presents the project activities and progress, as well as the public deliverables, the dissemination material, the newsletters, etc. Since the launching of the [STEP platform](#) (step.green), a plug-in has been added on the website’s homepage photo, enabling any interested visitor to be redirected to the platform. The private section is the Member’s Area, which was initially created to facilitate the project partners to exchange, upload and download files. However, the project partners decided that it would be more convenient to create a STEP wiki space in order to share documents.

The website activity is monitored using the Google Analytics, a tool that tracks and reports visitor traffic and gives a complete picture of the behaviour of the website audience. The following table briefly presents the data analysis for the STEP website’s visits.

Reporting period	June 2015 – May 2016	June 2016 – May 2017
Website sessions	1,234	1,934
Number of website visits	3,863	4,765
Website users	652	1,224
Average session duration (period)	4:30	2:38
Average percentage of new visitors per month	~51,99%	~62,25%
Average percentage of returning visitors per month	~48,01%	~37,8%

One notices that the number of website visits, of users and sessions increased. The rates of new visitors acquired every month (62,25%) reflect the success of the dissemination campaign. It should also be noted that the average session duration decreased, probably because users chose the option of the STEP platform through the plug-in on STEP’s homepage.

3.2 STEP blog

STEP blog is ready and has gone public since the beginning of 2017. YEE has created the blog and is responsible for the blog’s content and management. The material uploaded on the blog concerns articles, news, interviews etc. connected to the topics of STEP project.

The objectives of the STEP blog are to:

- make the STEP project known to as many young people as possible
- provide information/knowledge on the topics of youth participation, e-participation and the environment

So far, eight posts have been uploaded on the STEP blog. In particular, these posts concern:

- five interviews with YEE members & young people from environmental organizations
- three articles on participation related topics

YEE promotes the STEP blog through regular newsletters that sends to its members and its general network and through its social media accounts on Facebook. Until the end of May, the blog views were over 1,500, while posts on Facebook reached: 9.5K.

Figure 2: STEP blog

3.3 STEP Turkish Website

For the effective dissemination of the STEP project to Turkish politicians and stakeholders the Municipality of Hatay decided to create a website for the STEP project in Turkish language. The website can be accessed at the following link Step.hatay.bel.tr. This website contains information about the STEP project and objectives, as well as the STEP partners. Additionally, the website is being fed regularly with news and information about the activities organized by the Municipality of Hatay. So far the number of visits at the Turkish STEP website is 300.

Figure 3. HATAY's STEP website

3.4 Social media

The general social media accounts for the STEP project were created in Month 2. PLANO2 is the overall responsible for managing and feeding the general STEP social media accounts. These accounts will be preserved and be constantly fed with posts as they represent an effective way to be in touch with the STEP target groups, and especially young people.

Additional social media accounts dedicated to STEP were created, in order to disseminate the project and the STEP platform to each pilot area and reach a critical mass of young people that interact through such kinds of tools. These accounts were created and are managed by the corresponding pilot partner.

Although a respected number of users in social media has been acquired so far, the activity in these accounts is expected to raise in the next months, when additional dialogues will be created and uploaded in the STEP platform.

3.4.1 Facebook pages

The Facebook page of the STEP project can be found in the following link: <https://goo.gl/49OSG9>. Easy access to the Facebook page is also provided in each section of the project website. Otherwise, the page can be found by searching in Facebook for “STEP H2020 Project”.

The official language of the page is English. The STEP Facebook page has been created and is managed by PLANO2 and DRAXIS.

Figure 4.: STEP general Facebook page

Since Facebook is one of the most commonly held social media, most of the pilot partners decided to use it for the dissemination of their pilots' activities. Currently, apart from the general STEP Facebook page there are 3 more STEP Facebook pages and these are:

- Crete's pilot Facebook page: "@StepRegionCrete" (official language: Greek)
- Locride's pilot Facebook page: "@step h2020 locride" (official language: Italian)
- Valdemoro's pilot Facebook page: "@H2020 STEP Valdemoro" (official language: Spanish)

Figure 5: Crete's pilot Facebook page

Figure 6: Locride’s pilot Facebook page

Figure 7: Valdemoro’s pilot Facebook page

The activity of Facebook pages is monitored using the Facebook Insights which provides information about the page performance, including demographic data about the page audience, and shows how people are discovering and responding to the uploaded posts.

STEP Facebook page	Number of followers
General Facebook page	436
Crete’s pilot Facebook page	201
Locride’s pilot Facebook page	440
Valdemoro’s pilot Facebook page	63

The other two pilots, Mollet del Valles and HATAY decided to use their Municipality's general Facebook accounts in order to share the STEP news with the citizens.

3.4.2 Twitter

When it comes to quick crowdsourcing information, Twitter is the most effective one. STEP's general twitter account is used as a primary tool for spreading the project's news and announcements in real time and can be found at the following link: https://twitter.com/STEP_H2020. The name of the STEP Twitter account is "@STEP_H2020", while the preferred hashtag for the project tweets is "#STEP_H2020". Tweets are uploaded in a regular base and they refer to general information about youth STEP news and events. The STEP Twitter account is a useful channel to inform and engage with its target audiences.

Figure 8. General STEP twitter Account

The Locride's pilot has recently created a twitter account for the promotion of STEP. The name of the pilot's account is "@steplocride" and can be found at the following link: <https://twitter.com/steplocride>. Twitter activity is measured through follower users. The number of followers of the STEP general twitter account is 160, while the number of Locride's pilot account is 59.

Figure 9. Locride’s pilot STEP twitter Account

3.4.3 Instagram

Instagram is a quite widespread social media and its popularity has been growing steadily since it first debuted. It counts more than 500 million active users and the number of young people that use it is constantly increasing. For this reason, the pilot of Hatay and Locride decided to create additional Instagram accounts dedicated to STEP in order to engage young people in the pilot activities. The names of the Instagram accounts are:

- Hatay’s account: “projestep.hatay” with 2,690 followers
- Locride’s account: “steph2020locride” with 59 followers

Figure 10. Locride’s pilot STEP Instagram Account

3.4.4 Flickr account

Flickr is an online photo management and sharing application, that attracts the interest of a number of people. The pilot of Valdemoro decided to create a STEP account in this social media in order to present the activities performed by the Municipality concerning STEP. Flickr is also integrated with Facebook, so it is easier for the Municipality of Valdemoro to share the uploaded content with the respective facebook account. Currently, there are no followers in Valdemoro’s flickr account, but it has to be noted that that it counts 900 visits so far.

Figure 11. Valdemoro’s pilot STEP flickr Account

3.4.5 LinkedIn group

A STEP LinkedIn group was created at the beginning of the project. Its name is “STEP H2020 project” and it is available at the following link: <https://goo.gl/m5E6AQ>. However, since LinkedIn is a business-oriented social networking service, and during this period the consortium made every effort to attract young citizens, it was decided to focus on social media that attract the interest of young people. However, it was agreed to maintain the LinkedIn page and use it when the first results of the STEP solution will be available. So far, there are 76 members in the group of STEP in LinkedIn.

Figure 12. STEP LinkedIn Group

3.4.6 Google+ page

A Google+ page has been established in order to enable a link with the STEP YouTube presence and any further Google tool which will be adopted. A link has been made between the Google+ Page and the STEP website in order to provide more effective search results for those looking for topics relevant to STEP. The name of the STEP page in Google+ is “Step Horizon2020” and the page can be found in the following link: <https://goo.gl/d6xzJV>

However, since most of the young people prefer to use other social networking tools and the proportion of people that use Google + to interact is quite low, it was decided to maintain the Google + page, but not to use it as a core dissemination tool for STEP.

Figure 133. STEP Google + page

3.4.7 YouTube channel

The creation of audiovisual material for the promotion of the STEP project is of crucial importance as such tools are more attractive to young people. A YouTube channel has been created for the STEP project, under the name “STEP Horizon2020” and is available at <https://goo.gl/SkfgkJ>. So far, 15 videos have been uploaded on the channel and one playlist. More specifically, this channel contains:

- STEP’s promotional video in 6 languages, which provides general information about the project and addresses young people.
- 6 videos that provide information about STEP social media monitoring tool and its use.
- Presentations from STEP’s 1st Webinar titled “Let’s talk about e-participation”.
- A tutorial about STEP platform which describes how to navigate through the platform to young users.
- A tutorial about STEP platform which describes how to set up dialogues and manage content to the administrators.
- Video from the STEP webinar

Figure 144: STEP YouTube channel

3.5 STEP promotional material

3.5.1 Audiovisual material

In the first year of the project a short promotional video was created aiming at maximizing the visibility of STEP and explaining the objectives of the project in a stimulating way. As it was agreed in STEP's 4th project meeting on Crete, the STEP video had to be translated into each partner's language, so as to achieve greater inclusion and explain the project's objectives to non-English speakers. Thus, the STEP video was dubbed into Italian, Turkish and Greek and subtitled in Catalan, Spanish and Greek. All videos were uploaded on STEP YouTube channel and can be accessed at

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCgN3US8V79emiKrMGRYyiAw>. Additionally, STEP pilots uploaded the video on their social media accounts, webpages and presented it at their local Civil Service Centers, schools, events, etc.

Figure 155: Screen shot from YouTube

Apart from translating the STEP promotional video, additional videos were created and have been uploaded onto the channel since the beginning of June 2016. In particular, these 6 videos (tutorials) focus on the Social Media Monitoring Tool and they present:

- How to start monitoring a topic of interest in STEP
- How to perform free text search through collections
- How to refine the content of a collection to find valuable information
- How to browse through the content of a collection
- How to browse through “my collections” and customize them
- How to gain insight from collected data

All these videos have been used to create a playlist for STEP’s Social Media Monitoring Tool on the YouTube channel.

Two more tutorials have also been created by SAMPAS. The first one addresses young users and demonstrates navigation through the STEP platform, while the second one provides information to the administrators on how to set up and manage dialogues.

In the following screens, information from the YouTube analytics is briefly presented. The time period of these analytics is from the beginning of the project until the end of May 2017.

Geography	Watch time (minutes)	Views	Average view duration	Average percentage viewed
Greece	374 (52%)	604 (57%)	0:37	36%
Spain	72 (9.9%)	54 (5.1%)	1:19	74%
Italy	46 (6.4%)	63 (5.9%)	0:44	41%
Belgium	44 (6.1%)	73 (6.9%)	0:36	60%
United Kingdom	36 (5.1%)	45 (4.2%)	0:48	68%
Turkey	16 (2.2%)	30 (2.8%)	0:31	29%
Germany	15 (2.1%)	22 (2.1%)	0:41	69%
Romania	15 (2.1%)	10 (0.9%)	1:31	77%
United States	12 (1.7%)	14 (1.3%)	0:50	49%
Czechia	8 (1.2%)	17 (1.6%)	0:29	41%
Portugal	7 (0.9%)	9 (0.8%)	0:45	75%
Ukraine	5 (0.7%)	10 (0.9%)	0:30	22%
Georgia	4 (0.6%)	6 (0.6%)	0:43	74%
Canada	4 (0.6%)	5 (0.5%)	0:50	41%
Poland	4 (0.5%)	5 (0.5%)	0:45	76%
Australia	4 (0.5%)	13 (1.2%)	0:16	27%
India	3 (0.5%)	7 (0.7%)	0:29	13%
Finland	3 (0.4%)	3 (0.3%)	0:56	93%
Switzerland	3 (0.4%)	3 (0.3%)	0:53	90%
France	3 (0.4%)	5 (0.5%)	0:31	53%
Dominican Republic	3 (0.4%)	2 (0.2%)	1:17	129%
Nepal	2 (0.3%)	3 (0.3%)	0:43	73%
Indonesia	2 (0.3%)	3 (0.3%)	0:40	68%
Norway	2 (0.3%)	2 (0.2%)	0:59	99%
Ireland	2 (0.3%)	2 (0.2%)	0:59	98%

Figure 166: Views and watch time per country

As can be seen from Figure 15, the majority of video views mainly originate from Greece. It should be noted that the second country in video views is Belgium, where there are no STEP partners. This is a result of STEP’s comprehensive dissemination strategy, which focuses not only on pilot countries, but on the entire Europe.

Italy, Spain, the UK and Turkey follow at 3rd, 4th, 5th and 6th place, respectively. So far, the total number of views stands at 1,059; however, all partners should put extra effort in increasing STEP videos visibility.

Figure 17: Demographics of the STEP video's viewers

Regarding the demographics of viewers of STEP videos, 69% of them are men and 31% women, while the majority of the audience belongs to the 25-34 age group, i.e. part of the target group of the project (i.e 18-30 year-olds).

Figure 18: Traffic sources

Finally, Figure 18 indicates that the majority of video traffic comes from websites and apps that have embedded the videos or their links (42%), while the second traffic source is through the direct URL entry, bookmarks or unidentified apps (30%).

3.5.2 Newsletters

From June 2016 (M13) until May 2017 (M24) three newsletters were issued to inform all stakeholders about project news and progress.

The first one (i.e. the 2nd official newsletter) was sent at the beginning of July 2016 (M14). The topics addressed in that issue were:

- The concept of the STEP project
- Presentation of STEP video
- A research conducted by the STEP team on how social media can be used to engage young people
- Practical suggestions on how public authorities can engage young people in decision making procedures concerning environmental issues
- A brief presentation of the workshops organized in the context of STEP
- A brief presentation of the events STEP partners had participated in
- A brief description of synergies the STEP team had attempted to establish

The next newsletter (STEP's 3rd) was sent at the beginning of April 2017 (M23). Topics included in that newsletter were:

- The concept of the STEP platform
- An introduction to STEP pilots
- Information on the EU pilot concept and the meeting of the STEP team with the Chairwoman of the Environment, Public Health and Food Safety Committee of the European Parliament (ENVI Committee)
- Presentation of the STEP blog
- Information on the 1st STEP Webinar titled: "Let's talk about e-participation!"
- Information on relevant EU projects and initiatives

Both the 2nd and the 3rd newsletter were in English and they were shared with the STEP Network of Interest (NoI) members. In July 2016 STEP NoI comprised 962 members; this number increased to 1,010 members by April 2017. Additionally, both newsletters were uploaded on the project website and they were also sent to STEP partners so that they may distribute them via their communication channels.

Figure 19 First page of the 2nd STEP Newsletter

Figure 20 First page of the 3rd STEP Newsletter

The third newsletter was prepared by the Association of Communities of Locride area, STEP's Italian pilot partner, and the topics addressed in this issue were:

- STEP's Launch event in Locride
- STEP activities organized at the schools of Locride area
- The amendment of Sant'Agata del Bianco statute to make the use of online petition tools on Municipality issues mandatory
- The endorsement of the STEP project by the Municipality of Siderno
- The Environmental Observatory "Right to Life"

This newsletter was prepared in Italian and it was distributed within the network of the Italian pilot partner.

In order to engage as many stakeholders as possible, at least six additional newsletters will be prepared by the end of the project relating the project's progress and the pilot partners' activities.

Figure 21. First page of the 3rd STEP Newsletter

3.5.3 Printed Material

STEP's 2nd leaflet was prepared in July 2016 (M14). The STEP leaflet provides an overview of the project and it emphasizes on the technology behind the STEP platform, as well as on STEP key features. The leaflet has an attractive layout based on STEP's graphic identity and it is available in a double sided A5 paper format. It was agreed to be printed on recycled paper so that the environmental aspect of the project is reinforced.

Figure 22. Front & back side of STEP's 2nd leaflet

The 2nd STEP poster was prepared in English and each pilot partner was able to translate it so as to use it at project meetings, workshops, conferences and other events. The dimensions proposed for the poster printing are 85x200cm. The content of the poster may be modified throughout the duration of the project depending on needs and expectations at each dissemination event. Additional posters were designed and printed by each pilot partner.

step

Deciding together!

An ePlatform enabling youth's Societal and Political participation in the decision-making procedures concerning environmental issues.

Key Features:

- eParticipation
- Web / social media mining & visualization
- Machine translation
- Text-to-Speech tool

5 Pilot operations

- Madrid Municipality Spain
- Madrid Municipality Spain
- Associação Municipal de Comunidade Autónoma da Madeira Madeira Portugal
- Republic of Cyprus Cyprus
- Madrid Municipality Municipality Turkey

Learn more about STEP www.step4youth.eu

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Figure 23. 2nd STEP poster

As initially discussed, pilot partners would design additional promotional material to ensure maximum dissemination of the project and to meet their own dissemination needs. To this end, pilot partners printed posters in different dimensions and the Mollet del Valles pilot designed further promotional material in order to cover the needs at different occasions. In this context, Mollet del Valles designed and printed:

- 5,000 bookmarks which were distributed at an event that took place in the public library
- 2,000 adhesive labels, which were placed in flower pots and distributed to participants

Figure 24: STEP Bookmarks

Figure 25: STEP adhesive labels for flower pots

4 General dissemination activities performed up to M24

The following sections outline the general dissemination activities that were carried out in the period June 2016 – May 2017 (M13- M24) by all project partners.

4.1 Network of Interest

The establishment and maintenance of the STEP Network of Interest (NoI) is an ongoing process that spans throughout the entire lifetime of the STEP project. STEP NoI is well-established, since the initial goal of 1,000 members had been achieved by the end of November 2016. Today STEP NoI counts more than 1,100 members from 43 countries. The members of the NoI derive from four sources:

- a) extensive search through the Internet
- b) network of each partner
- c) b2b meetings with stakeholders during partners' participation in events
- d) stakeholders subscribed to the STEP newsletter.

A number of online and offline activities have been/ will be implemented in order to maintain the network, keep its members updated on STEP's news and enrich it with additional stakeholders; all these activities are described in detail in D7.6 – 2nd Network of Interest.

4.2 Press Releases & Publications

A number of press releases have been sent from STEP pilot partners in order to update both potential stakeholders and users on the STEP solution and the running/upcoming dialogues of pilots. Additionally, the partners gave interviews at local TV stations and radios in order to present STEP and the running / upcoming dialogues. The table below presents relevant press releases:

Partner	Topic	URL / type of media	Date
ROC	STEP Launch Event in Chania	http://bit.ly/2qWAXkI	17/05/2017
ROC	STEP Launch Event in Heraklion	http://bit.ly/2r60eHq	17/05/2017
ROC	Meeting with STEP core team	http://bit.ly/2rVy1Hh	16/12/2016
ROC	5 th STEP Project meeting in Prague	http://bit.ly/2r5TVUo	9/12/2016
HATAY	Event on the occasion of the National Sovereignty and Children's Day Celebration Festivals	http://bit.ly/2rY0c8F	23/04/2017
HATAY	Advertisement at "Ejderya" (Monthly Journal)	Local newspaper	April 2017
HATAY	Participation of the STEP team in the Book Fair in Antakya	http://bit.ly/2sFTx7	15/05/2017
CSB	Introduction to the STEP Platform	Various local newspapers	2/05/2017
MDV	Launch of the STEP Platform	Advertisements at the following local newspapers: - 4 Cantons - Contrapunt - Mollet a mà	4/03/2017
MDV	Launch of a new dialogue about participatory budgeting	http://bit.ly/2sVYDVW	22/05/2017
MDV	Advertisements about the dialogue "Gallecs, your park. Come and enjoy it"	Advertisements in the following local newspapers: - 4 Cantons - Contrapunt - Mollet a mà	24/02/2017
MDV	Advertisements about the dialogue "Blossomed Mollet"	Advertisements in the following local newspapers: - 4 Cantons - Contrapunt - Mollet a mà	23/02/2017
MDV	Press Release about the Popular Calçotada event	Local newspapers: - 4 cantons - Mollet a mà - Contrapunt	
MDV	Presentation of the Popular	Local TV: Vallès Visió	23/02/2017

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	Calçotada event		
MDV	Press Release about the Tree Day event	Local newspapers: - 4 cantons - Mollet a mà - Contrapunt	5/03/2017
MDV	Presentation of the Popular Calçotada event	Local TV: Vallès Visió	5/03/2017
MDV	Advertisements about the dialogue "Urban garden of Can Borrell"	Advertisements in the following local newspapers: - 4 Cantons - Contrapunt - Mollet a mà	15/03/2017
VLD	Targeted event for introducing the STEP platform to directors of educational institutions	http://bit.ly/2rYdlcs	20/09/2016
VLD	Event for the presentation of STEP at the Youth House	http://bit.ly/2sGbTid	25/11/2016
VLD	STEP photocall in carnival event	http://bit.ly/2r23zYG	25/02/2017
VLD	STEP Launch Event	http://bit.ly/2siucNc	10/03/2017
VLD	Event for the presentation of STEP	http://bit.ly/2r4JuFx	27/01/2017
VLD	Presentation of STEP at EXPOEDUCATIVA 2017	http://bit.ly/2r8qNf4	22/03/2017
MDV	Presentation of STEP in the framework of the Spring festival at the local TV	TV channel Vallès Visió	2/04/2017
MDV	Presentation of STEP in the framework of the Spring festival	The press release was presented in the following newspapers - 4 cantons - Mollet a mà - Contrapun	2/04/2017
VLD	Presentation of STEP at "SAN MARCOS FESTIVITY 2017"	http://bit.ly/2sikKt6	25/04/2017
VLD	Presentation of STEP at an Event organized in the framework of the World Environment Day	http://bit.ly/2rDTG6i	4/06/2017

Apart from the publications in the local and national press, a scientific paper was published in the framework of the e-Gov2016 conference. The Conference took place in September at Guimaraes, in Portugal. ABERTAY was responsible for the preparation, as well as the presentation of the paper.

4.3 *Person-to-person meetings*

A number of meetings have already taken place for effective dissemination and full valorisation of the STEP solution. The pilot partners have organised meetings with representatives of local authorities and youth population in their area. The respective reports are presented in the relevant [Pilots Chapter](#).

Additional meetings have been organized by the rest of the consortium. More specifically, the STEP team agreed to use the platform at Pan-European level, in the framework of a general European pilot test, which will invite young people to voice their opinions on general issues concerning the environment.

For this purpose, the STEP team seeks Environmental NGOs and other Agencies that could possibly use the platform in order to create a timeline, a questionnaire, or initiate an e-petition and ask young European citizens to share their opinions on specific environmental topics. Information about the meeting could be found below.

Meeting with Resilient Thessaloniki

In October 2016 the STEP team in Thessaloniki arranged for a meeting with the representatives of the Municipality of Thessaloniki in order to demonstrate the STEP platform and explore possibilities for future collaboration. During the meeting, the representative of the Municipality pointed out that in 2014, Thessaloniki was selected as one of the 100 Resilient Cities (100RC)¹ network and that the Municipality established the 'Resilient Thessaloniki' body. In this context, the city needs to undertake a number of activities in order to enhance active and continuous participation of the diverse stakeholders of the city. Resilient Thessaloniki expressed an interest in using the STEP tool as an additional STEP pilot. The two parties agreed and in May 2017, Resilient Thessaloniki uploaded the first dialogue on the STEP platform.

Meeting with the Chairwoman of the ENVI Committee of the European Parliament

The STEP team has already had two meetings with Mrs Adina-Ioana VĂLEAN, Chairwoman of the Environment, Public Health and Food Safety Committee of the European Parliament (ENVI Committee). Both meetings took place at the offices of the ENVI Committee, at the European Parliament. During the meetings the STEP team presented the project and the platform focusing specifically on the social media monitoring tool and the timeline, two basic features that could be instantly used by the ENVI Committee. Additionally, it was noted that the STEP platform could be used by the ENVI Committee as a unique tool that not only would raise youth awareness on the environmental issues the ENVI Committee is in charge of, but would also foster young people's empowerment and active participation in democratic life. The feedback received by Mrs Valean was very positive and she pointed out that the graphic identity of the platform is quite user friendly and welcoming for young users. Mrs Valean volunteered to introduce the STEP Platform to the members of the ENVI Committee and to investigate possible ways of collaboration.

Meeting with BRAL

Citizens Action Brussels (BRAL) is a city movement striving to make Brussels sustainable and build an environmentally friendly, affordable and solidary city. BRAL organises actions, lobbying groups, supports citizens' initiatives and provides advice to the authorities. The STEP team met the representatives of BRAL at their offices in Brussels and presented the STEP platform to them. Discussions followed on how they could

¹ http://www.100resilientcities.org/#/_/

support the dissemination of the tool and how they could use it in order to interact with citizens on atmospheric pollution issues and create related dialogues. It was agreed to organize an online presentation in order to demonstrate the STEP platform to additional members of BRAL.

Meeting with additional local authorities:

Additional online and offline meetings with representatives of authorities / youth and environmental organizations took place within the last year of the project. During these meetings the representatives of the STEP team presented the objectives of the project and demonstrated the platform. The overall feedback received by representatives of the agencies was quite positive. They were quite interested in the STEP solution; however at that time period it was not possible to use the STEP platform, due to limited human resources, or because it had not been part of their original strategic plan. These are the stakeholders that the STEP consortium had meetings with:

- Meeting with Granada Deputation, Spain
- Meeting with Granada City Council, Spain
- Meeting with Madrid en Bici (NGO), Spain
- Meeting with Amigos de la Tierra (NGO), Spain
- Meeting with the Municipality of Chalandri, Greece
- Online meeting with the ecological youth organization FÖJ Aktiv e.V. (Germany)

4.4 Collaboration with similar projects/ initiatives

The STEP consortium identified and reached similar projects and initiatives with the aim of collaborating with them. Through these collaborations information, views and experiences on topics of common interest were exchanged, while the possibility of synergies was explored.

In particular, the STEP team established strong synergies with the consortia of three European projects, [EUth](#), [EMPATIA](#) and, [CatchEYou](#) and had a number of calls with representatives of these projects in order to exchange information and dissemination practices. It should also be noted that Mrs Kerstin Franzl, the coordinator of the [EUth](#), is a member of the STEP Advisory Board and Mr Lorenzo Floresta, the Dissemination Manager of the [CatchEYou](#) has recently joined the STEP Advisory Board. Mr Floresta also participated in the 6th STEP project meeting in Siderno and made a presentation titled: “Engaging youth in policy making. Bringing policy closer to young people”

4.5 1st STEP Webinar

The first STEP webinar took place on Monday, 14 of March 2017. Two European projects, which are in close co-operation with the STEP consortia were invited to join the webinar and make presentations on the work they had accomplished and their plans for the future. After the presentations, a lively Q&A session followed and a fruitful discussion took place on how the municipalities can engage young users in decision making, what the next plans of each project are and how such kinds of tools can be effectively promoted. Additionally, participants had the opportunity to provide their feedback on STEP and the other two e-participation tools.

1 s t W e b i n a r

Let's talk about e-participation!

When? Tuesday 14 March 11am (CET)

Three European projects about - e-participation, STEP, EMPATIA and EUTH will e-meet at a unique webinar on Tuesday, 14 of March 2017, at 11am (CET).

STEP: The interactive platform enabling youth Societal and Political e-Participation in decision-making procedures concerning environmental issues.

EMPATIA: The first hands-on digital platform for creating and managing a coherent participatory system that integrates multiple channels of engagement in a single solution.

Euth: The European project that has developed OPIN solution: an all-in-one digital and mobile participation toolbox, which can be embedded in the web presence of youth organisations or public administrations.

Who can Join? We welcome youth workers, participation experts, software developers, employees in user organizations, or any other party interested in digital participation.

SUBSCRIBE TO JOIN!

11:00-11:45: What will you learn if you join the webinar:
Welcome / Introduction
Christodoulos Keratidis, Project Manager, STEP project

What is the STEP platform, how it works and what are the partners' future plans
Maria Vogiatzi, Dissemination Manager, STEP Project

The tools and solutions that have been developed in the framework of the EMPATIA project
Michelangelo Secchi, Scientific Coordinator, H2020 EMPATIA Project
Kalinca Copello, Researcher, H2020 EMPATIA Project

What has been achieved so far in the EUTH project - the second launch of the OPIN.me platform
Evaldas Rupkus, Project Manager for Marketing, EUTH Project

11:45-12:15: Any questions?
 Interactive discussion

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

Figure 26: Agenda -Invitation of the 1st STEP Webinar

An invitation was sent to all members of the Network of Interest and relevant posts were uploaded in STEP's social media accounts. Additionally, the event was disseminated through Facebook pages and other sites.

Figure 27: Post of the 1st STEP Webinar on the joinup page

4.6 Participation in studies

The STEP team is always eager to participate in studies and initiatives that will enhance the dissemination of the project. So far, STEP team has participated in the two studies described below:

The first one was implemented by KPMG Advisory S.p.A. with the European Commission – DIGIT Unit B.4 on the use of Social Media Analysis tools and activities as a data source to support decision and policy-making by EU public administrations, namely “Leveraging Social Media full potential to increase citizen engagement and participation in PAs decision-making processes”. STEP was selected to be part of the study as a good practice and guideline use case in order to foster sharing and reuse of relevant solutions.

The title of the second study is: “The Impact of the Internet and Social Media on Youth Participation and Youth Work”. This study is carried out by the Open Evidence for the European Commission (EACEA). STEP will be used as a case study for this project.

4.7 Participation in events

The table below presents the events that the STEP partners have participated in, in order to promote the STEP project and create synergies with other stakeholders from various countries. The events that STEP pilots have participated / organized are presented in the respective [Pilots Chapter](#).

Partner	Title of Activity	Brief description	Reach	Date
YEE	European Youth Event (discussion panels,	The event aimed at creating a forum for people to exchange ideas and perspectives on youth-related issues, developing solutions to resolve issues in Europe and meeting with European	~ 20	20-21/05/2016

	workshops, stands etc.), Spain	decision-makers and experienced speakers. YEE representative presented the STEP project to a number of young people.		
ABERTAY	Contemporary Political Youth Culture and Communication Symposium, UK	The Centre for Political Youth Culture and Communication (CPAC) is dedicated to exploring socio-cultural factors influencing the civic engagement of young people and its means of communication. The styles, nature and means of their political engagement is, therefore, of increasing significance to policy-makers and the academia alike. Presenting the STEP project to this audience raised much wider awareness about the project's outcomes. A large number of people with similar interests were present, including the representative of EU H2020 funded Catch EyoU, whom the STEP team had the opportunity to discuss and establish synergies with.	~70	18-19/07/16
DRAXIS	Science Communication Event, UK	The goal of the event was to inform scientists/project coordinators about the importance of communicating their projects to a wider audience, as well as to introduce effective communication techniques. The event was organized by the European Commission. The initial plan was to present STEP at the event. However, due to lack of time, some presentations, including STEP's, had to be canceled. Still, the event was a great opportunity to network with representatives from other EU H2020 projects.	~ 10	24/07/2016
YEE	Training course "Act, React & E-act!", Prague	The training course examined how digital media had shaped society, how communication technologies were being used & misused, and how organisations and activists could genuinely mobilize citizens, educate, make positive changes and build a stronger community with the help of the Internet. YEE Networking Coordinator was a participant in the training course. She organised a workshop about ways to engage young people in e-participation. The STEP project was also presented. Participants learnt about how they could benefit from the STEP platform, asked questions and some of them signed up for the newsletter.	~ 10	01-07/08/2016
ABERTAY	e-Gov2016	e-Gov is one of the greatest Conferences in the		05-08/09/2016

	conference, Portugal	field of e-participation and it is implemented every year in different countries. ABERTAY participated in the event and present the paper that had prepared about STEP.		
DRAXIS	“Thessaloniki Climathon: Inspiring behavioral change for a climate friendly city”, Greece	Climathon is a 24 hour hackathon event that is organized concurrently at different cities. In 2016 Climathon was organized in 59 cities around the world. The organisation of Climathon in Thessaloniki was an opportunity to open a broad discussion on climate change for the first time. During these 24 hours a number of interesting and interactive presentations were held, while all participants had to discuss and come up with innovative and feasible solutions to address climate change challenges. The members of the STEP team not only presented the project, but also participated in the event as mentors.	~ 40	22-23/10/2016
DRAXIS	#BePart Summit, Germany	#BePart is a 3-day event organized for European youth workers, participation experts, software developers, user organizations and other stakeholders and focuses on one basic aim: to bring them all together in order to share good practices and experiences on e-participation and to identify challenges and opportunities. The STEP team was there in order to present the project and the STEP platform to the Summit, interact with other stakeholders and create synergies with youth organizations.	47	14-16/11/2016
INMARK	National congress on the environment (CONAMA)	Conama is a biennial congress at which an extensive network of people, companies and entities interested in sustainability collaborate and cooperate to share experiences and visions. CONAMA 2016 received more than 7000 people and provided more than 150 technical sessions, which included technical committees and working groups. Representatives from 500 cities/municipalities contributed with their professional experience. This event had very high impact on the STEP project as it was an effective channel to create awareness of project objectives. A presentation of the STEP platform to 80 people during a working group session (GT-4 -Sustainable Mobility Plans in Spain – Coordinated by Gea21) took place, which was the starting point of communication with non-	~ 80	27-30/11/2016

		governmental organizations, such as Greenpeace, WFF, ColectYvo and Red de Ciudades en Bicicleta.		
YEE	Volunteering day with YEE at the Toulcuv Dvur eco-center, Prague	The event aimed at promoting volunteering, outdoor activities and the work of NGOs or non-profit organisations, in this case, the Toulcuv Dvur eco-center and YEE. YEE prepared an interactive game to calculate the ecological footprint of each participant. During the event the STEP video was played, the project was presented and STEP leaflets were distributed.	12	17/11/2016
DRAXIS	1 st CATCH-EyoU Conference	CATCH-EyoU is a research and innovation action funded by the European Commission under the H2020 Programme. Through an inter-disciplinary (e.g., psychology, education, political science, sociology, media and communications) contribution, the first open conference of CATCH-EyoU aimed at exploring the multifaceted issues that influence various forms of youth active engagement in Europe, thus offering policy makers and professionals working with young people new instruments and “conceptual lenses” to better understand this generation and bring the EU closer to all its citizens. The STEP team made a presentation about the STEP project at the session “Digital participation of European youth”.	~250	2-4/05/2017

5 Pilot partners dissemination activities

The Deliverable 7.7, 2nd Dissemination plan, presents the local dissemination plan of the STEP pilots. Pilot partners followed the general framework of this deliverable and adapted it according to their special needs and the timeframe that was more convenient to them. According to D 7.7, each STEP pilot partner had to establish a core group of users and organize a workshop with them in order to discuss possible methods of engaging young people in STEP and local events. Moreover, when the STEP platform would be ready, each pilot partner would organise one launch event. These launch events would aim in introducing the STEP platform to the general public and allowing the testing of the STEP concept in a wide audience. As it had been initially foreseen, a number of workshops and other events would be organized in pilots’ local areas. This chapter presents the dissemination activities and the events each pilot partner organized/participated in.

5.1 Region of Crete

The Region of Crete has developed a comprehensive local communication strategy in order to promote the STEP project to young citizens and encourage them to participate in decision making procedures. In this context the Region of Crete has presented STEP to a number of local and national events organized in different cities of Crete, while two launch events took place at Heraklion and Chania.

5.1.1 Dissemination Events

The dissemination activities of Crete's pilot are briefly presented below.

Title of Activity	Brief description	Reach	Date
6th Conference in Maritime Spatial Planning Worldwide (MSP)	A chance to raise awareness about the STEP project and present the need of active youth participation in decision making procedures for marine spatial planning in coastal-marine areas.	120	23-24/06/2016
5th international conference on industrial and hazardous waste management	The participation in the event aimed to create awareness about the project to students and possible local stakeholders attending the conference, as well as to create synergies with stakeholders (professors of the Technical university of Crete, e.t.c.) of the Regional Unit of Chania.	270	27-30/09/2016
"Researcher's Night", Foundation for Research and Technology – Hellas (FORTH)	"Researcher's Night" is an annual open event for people to get to know the world of science through numerous scientific happenings. The Region of Crete participated with an interactive presentation of the STEP project.	198	30/09/16
Education Environmental Centers of Crete	The event was organized by the Environmental Education Center of Vamos in order all four Environmental Centers of Crete to present their programs and activities for the current school year. The Region of Crete held the opening speech and presented the STEP project, as an important initiative for reaching young people.	30	10/10/2016
4th Chania Film Festival	The event was organized by Chania Film Festival organization and took place in Chania Cultural Center. It is a ten-day annual festival enhanced with parallel activities, exhibitions, courses for schools etc. During the festival the Region of Crete disseminated relevant information material for STEP.	1,000	26/10/2016-7/11/2016
Event of the School of Environmental Engineering	The event was organized by the School of Environmental Engineering of the Technical University of Crete within the Postgraduate course. The Region of Crete was invited to present the project scope and objectives, as well as the	32	24/11/2016

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Technical University of Crete	platform to postgraduate students of environmental studies. Even though these students have great knowledge of technical issues, most of them ignore the decision making procedures for environmental issues. So, young people were informed about the intention of the Region of Crete to ask for their consultation and also about the new e-participation tool they can use, the STEP platform.		
Workshop with the core team	Representatives from the following institutes and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) took part in the Workshop: 1. Natural History Museum of Crete, University of Crete 2. Technical Educational Institute of Crete 3. Environmental Education Center of Anogia 4. Environmental Education Center of Archanes 5. Hellenic Speleological Society – Institute of Speleological Research 6. Minoistas (NGO promoting volunteering in various actions) 7. Ecological Intervention in Iraklion (Environmental NGO) During the workshop the participants discussed the events that will be organized within the next months and an interactive brainstorming session took place.	15	15/12/2017
Presentation to the Red cross volunteers & other NGO's members	The purpose of the presentation was to inform the audience about the deliverables of two EU projects, one of which was the STEP project and platform.	23	21/02/2017
"Ask and Learn", Young People professional Orientation	The event was organized by the Directorate of Secondary Education and the Union of Parents of Chania at the Cultural Center in order for the representatives of various Universities, Unions, etc, to provide career advices to young people. Exploiting the occasion, the Region of Crete introduced the STEP platform to the audience and encouraged them to use it.	1,600	11-12/03/2017
Technical University of Crete "Open Day of Acquaintance"	The event was organized by the Technical University of Crete with the help of volunteer students aiming in introducing Schools to the campus facilities. Exploiting the occasion, the Region of Crete made a presentation in order to inform the audience (young people, students and pupils) about the STEP project and encourage young people to sign in the platform and participate in the dialogues. During the event, it was noticed that the students were far more interested in the platform than pupils. There was also a request from the students for an indoor presentation of the platform.	~1600	3/4/2017
STEP Launch Events at Heraklion &	The events were organized by the Region of Crete in order to announce to the general public the pilot use of the STEP platform. A presentation of the project, its scope and the	30	12/5/2017 & 18/05/2017

Chania	local pilot plan was made. Moreover, the platform was presented to public, while laptops and tablets with Internet connection were available to participants in order to register and use the platform. The event raised the awareness of the general public on the project, since a number of online and printed articles published the launching of the new e-participation tool. After the presentations, a useful discussion followed regarding the public mistrust of local authorities and how the platform will help changing it.		
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In the next months the Region of Crete has planned to implement / participate in the following activities:

- 24/5/2017: Technical University of Crete: Presentation of the STEP project and the platform - Open Invitation to students from all Departments, Chania
- 10-11/06/2017, P_public festival: Presentation of the STEP project and platform during the festival, Chania
- 29-30/05/2017 Info point during the “First Scholarship of Crete for Athletics and Culture “ , Heraklion
- September 2017: Researcher's night organized by FORTH
- July 2017: Cretan Diet Fest

5.1.2 *Communication with local stakeholders*

The Region of Crete established a number of synergies with the following stakeholders:

- **Technical University of Crete.** The public relationships office of the Technical University has supported the promotion of the STEP project during a number of events. Their support not only included the provision of technical facilities (room, internet, etc), but also the dissemination of the STEP project, through their students’ mailing lists.
- **Technological Institute of Crete.** A representative of the Institute has already participated in the workshop organized in December and committed to further participate in the project.
- **WWF** Collaboration so far includes the presentation of the STEP platform during an event they organized about Cretan wetlands, while discussions took place on additional activities that could
- **ARCHELON**, a Sea Turtle Protection Society volunteered to promote the dialogue regarding protected species, and participate in dialogues regarding Environmental Studies of units that threat *Caretta Caretta*.
- **Environmental Educational Centers** committed to promote the STEP platform to students through their programs. They also participated in STEP’s workshop and events, offering their experience about making the dialogues more attractive to young people.
- **Regional Directorate of Secondary and Primary Education.** This is a recent collaboration with a new stakeholder at Heraklion. It should be noted that this stakeholders belongs to the Greek Ministry of Education. Through this collaboration an additional presentation of the STEP platform has been arranged.

Additional stakeholders that the Region of Crete is planning to engage in STEP:

- **P_public group in Chania.** It is a very active group of young participants that performs events of various themes, social and environmental. The events they organize this year on 10 and 11/06/2017 concern the use and accessibility of public space. During these events there will be a presentation of the STEP Platform. Additionally, they agreed in promoting STEP events to their members.
- **TEDx:** An active organization of youth people.

5.2 *Mollet del Vallès Municipality*

STEP became an important tool for Mollet del Valles Municipality. Prior to the launch of an environmental public dialogue, the Municipality creates a private one for the members of the City Council, in order to exchange views and ideas on the topic and set up the public dialogue in detail and more effectively. In terms of dissemination, Mollet del Valles Municipality has developed an integrated online and offline communication plan, which consists of the organization of various events, two launch events, the production of additional promotional material reported, advertisements at local newspapers, info kiosks, etc.

5.2.1 *Dissemination Events*

The dissemination activities of Mollet del Valles pilot are briefly presented below.

Title of Activity	Brief description	Reach	Date
STEP workshop with the core team	The workshop with the Core team was implemented at the premises of the Municipality. The Municipality of Mollet presented the platform and the pilot plan and expressed concerns on how young people could be reached in order to participate in decision making procedures. A lively discussion followed during which the members of the core team expressed their thoughts and ideas on the activities that could be organized for that purpose	15	22/12/2016
Stand at the Biblioteca Can Mula	4 Public High Schools of Mollet del Vallès visited the library during this month. An info kiosk was set at the building of the Municipality in order to inform students about the STEP project, while 5.000 STEP bookmarks were disseminated.	~60	February 2017
Launch Event of the STEP Platform - Tree Day Event	The environmental department of the City Council organizes this event yearly. It consists on giving citizens the possibility to plant 2.000 trees to make a green contribution to the city. STEP was also presented at Tree Day 2016. Some of the actions carried out during the event are the following: information stand of STEP Project; distribution of STEP brochures; presentation of STEP's second public dialogue.	~300	05/03/2017
Launch Event of the STEP Platform	Popular Calçotada is an annual event that attracts the interest of more than 800 citizens. Calçot is a type of scallion	~800	5/03/2017

- Popular Calçotada	or green onion. The most traditional way of eating calçots is at a calçotada, an annual gastronomical celebration held between November and April, where barbecued calçots are consumed in massive quantities. The Municipality set up an info kiosk for the STEP Project, distributed diptychs and presented the first uploaded dialogue in STEP platform.		
Green Point Information	The environmental department of the City Council every month sets up a green point within city's outdoors market. Which consists an important opportunity for the dissemination of environmental actions and projects. Mollet del Vallet joined the stand and informed citizens of all ages about the STEP platform and the dialogues that are open in the platform.	~300	14/03/2017
Spring Festival	The participants of that event are mainly families. This event focuses on the creation of urban gardens in public spaces and it is enhanced with a number of parallel events, such as clown show, cooking workshop, etc. During this event an info kiosk was set up and the representatives of the Municipality distributed flyers and informed citizens about the STEP solution.	700	2/04/2017

Mollet del Valles Municipality intends to organize one or two events in collaborating with the Center for Young People called l'ERA.

5.2.2 *Communication with local stakeholders*

Mollet Del Valles established a number of synergies with the following stakeholders:

- **L'Era: Centre for Young People** (public body). Mollet del Valles has arranged several meetings with the Municipality's network of civic and cultural centers to present STEP and engage them in the project's dissemination strategy. The results of that communication were very positive, since they supported the promotion of the Municipality's dialogue: "Urban Garden of Can Borrel" and more than 100 users participated in that dialogue as users.
- **Network of Civic and cultural centres** (public bodies). In the framework of this collaboration, Mollet del Valles Municipality placed a roll up about STEP in all the centers. Additionally, the centers supported the dissemination of the STEP platform and the dialogues by sending emails to more than 3,000 citizens.
- **Geoblau** (private Company). This company is active in the field of the environment and has supported the promotion of the STEP platform, by disseminating it through its network of contacts that include several institutions, primary schools, associations, etc.
- **Agroecological Association** of Gallecs (active in the organic agriculture field).
- **Consortium of Gallecs** (Public body - active in the field of the environment).

The two abovementioned stakeholders have supported the first dialogue by disseminating it in their social media and by inviting citizens to join the dialogue. The Municipality is planning to involve them in two

additional dialogues on “itineraries” and “food policy” that will be uploaded in the STEP platform after the summer period.

- **Secondary schools.** The political representative for education and the responsible for European projects officer of Mollet del Valles visited a number of schools in order to present STEP. Municipality considers as a milestone the fact that trust has been created between the two parties and that they will support the promotion of the STEP solution. As a first output, the teacher of “Natural Sciences” is currently working together with the Municipality’s officers of the Environmental and Participation Department on the creation of a dialogue dedicated to students.

Meetings with stakeholders that didn’t thrive:

- Morats i Torrats (association)
- Culture and Young People

Mollet del Valles tried to engage these two actors of the city, who also coordinate the Summer Festival. Even though they were very interested in the STEP project they could not proceed with the collaboration due to limited human resources.

Additional stakeholders that the Mollet del Vallet Municipality is planning to engage in STEP:

- Esplai Xivarri (association) - Education and Young People
- Club Muntanyenc (association) - Sport and nature
- Tuareg (association) - Education and Young People

Additionally, since the Municipality is planning to launch a dialogue on the improvement of the food policy, stakeholders active in the food sector will be contacted. Some of them are:

- Private catering companies
- Local producers
- Retailers
- Local Market (indoor and outdoor)
- Parents Associations

5.3 *Valdermoro Municipality*

Valdemoro Municipality has implemented a number of dissemination activities with a special focus on schools and high school students. One of the Municipality’s basic goals is to inspire behavioral change to this target group and to engage them to participate in decision making from a very early stage. A number of co-creation workshops were also organized with high school students for raising awareness of young people on environmental issues.

5.3.1 Dissemination Events

The dissemination activities of Valdemoro's pilot are briefly presented below.

Title of Activity	Brief description	Reach	Date
Breakfast with directors of Educational Institutions	The 2 nd Breakfast with directors of educational institutions was implemented on September 2016. An update on the work performed was presented and a lively discussion followed on two basic topics: -youth engagement in policy making - raising environmental awareness of young people	41	20/09/2016
STEP Youth House	The STEP Youth House was an event that gathered young people, environmental organizations, as well as political leaders of Valdemoro. During the event the participants exchanged knowledge and ideas on local environmental issues, while discussions were held on how the ecological environment could be improved and what possible activities could be implemented in local level.	29	25/11/16
Workshop with the core team	Young people from High Schools participated in this event in order to be informed about the STEP platform and discuss with the STEP team effective ways and activities in order to engage young people in the STEP tool. During this event, it was decided that the STEP team should participate in 5 big events organized in Valdemoro.	17	27/12/2016
Tribute to teachers	For the purposes of the Tribute a display of photos demonstrating the importance of the protection of the environment in schools was set, while a theatrical play on how young people accept and use technology took place. The main goal of the event was to present young people's technological habits and to showcase how they could use STEP in their everyday life, in order to participate in decision making for the protection of the environment.	195	27/01/17
Step photocall in carnival event	Valdemoro's STEP team participated in the parades and the activities of the Valmemoro Carnivall. An interesting photocall with information about STEP was set at the town square and young people could take photos of themselves and upload them on Valdemoro's STEP Facebook page. Costumes made with recycled materials received positive feedback and comments by the STEP team.	1,500	25/02/17
Presentation of the STEP platform	The official launching event of STEP was organized at the main Auditorium of the city. A number of students and representatives of environmental associations participated at the event which included three sessions. During the first session the STEP project was presented and a live demonstration of the platform took place. The second session was a round table discussion on the topic "Efficient exploitation of the environmental resources in Valdemoro", while the third session was a music concert.	160	10/03/2017

Expoeducativa 2017	The purpose of this event was to inform young people about the educational opportunities offered in the municipality and the region in general. A stand about STEP was also set at Expoeducativa in order to inform young people about the youth e-participation procedures.	~800	22/03/2017 - 27/03/2017
San Marcos Festivity 2017	San Marcos festivity took place at the natural park Bolitas del Airón in Valdemoro. During the event a STEP info kiosk was set in order to inform young people about the open dialogues and motivate them to register in the platform and participate. Additionally, in the framework of the dialogue “Cuidemos nuestros parques” a relevant activity took place, where a group of young volunteers collected the waste found at the park.	~750	25/04/17
Workshop with students of maestro Matías bravo High school	During the workshop, a presentation of the STEP project took place, while a live demonstration of the platform followed. The participants of the workshop were interested in discussing a number of local environmental issues that were about to be brought in the STEP platform.	27	18/05/17
Meeting with young people from la Morada;	The purpose of the event was to create an action plan for the inclusion of young people who grow in a difficult family Environment. After a large conversation on how to include these groups of young people in societal participation a presentation of the STEP platform followed and the participants were invited to join the STEP dialogues.	5	19/05/17 and 23/05/17
Workshop with people with disabilities	The purpose of the event was to demonstrate the STEP platform to the participants of the workshop and train them on how to use it.	6	19/05/17

Until the end of the project, Valdemoro Municipality has planned to implement / participate in the following activities:

- Reforest “Castle Park”: Call the youth and their families of Valdemoro Municipality to plant trees at the city park within the occasion of the World Environment Day (5 June 2017).
- Bicycle Festival: The students of the Institutes of Valdemoro organize the bicycle part inviting citizens to participate in a tour of a natural park of Valdemoro (21 June 2017)
- Clean Arroyo de la Cañada stream: Support the proposal of environmental associations to convene young people, residents of Valdemoro and other associations to clean the banks of the stream, and participate in other activities organized for this purpose.

5.3.2 *Communication with local stakeholders*

The Municipality of Valdemoro has regular meetings with a number of stakeholders in order to discuss the progress of the pilot plan and involve them in the STEP activities and events.

Within the next months the Municipality will contact additional associations and clubs related to the topics that will be uploaded on the STEP platform (cycling, sports, urban planning associations, etc).

5.4 Hatay Metropolitan Municipality

Hatay's Metropolitan Municipality has created strong synergies with Mustafa Kemal University and other local NGO's for the promotion of the STEP platform to young citizens. A number of local workshops and events have been organized since April 2016 and additional ones are going to take place within the next months. Hatay Municipality has uploaded two dialogues on the platform and is planning to upload an additional one until the middle of the April.

5.4.1 Dissemination Events

The dissemination activities of Hatay's pilot are briefly presented below.

Title of Activity	Brief description	Reach	Date
Meeting with stakeholders	The basic goal of this meeting was to present STEP to the Public Education Center Authority in Antakya and to the Antakya Environmental Protection Association. A number of young students and volunteers attended the presentation, while strong synergies created with both the agencies who decided to support the dissemination of the project.	35	26/09/2016
Infoday- meeting	Two info-days were organized during November 2016 for Mustafa Kemal University students. The feedback gathered for the Municipality's new e-participation tool was very positive and some participants expressed their interest in participating in Municipality's internal exercise for the testing of the platform.	40	17/ 11/ 2016 – 25/ 11/ 2016
Co-Design Creative Workshop Step HATAY Metropolitan Municipality	A Co- Design Creative Workshop at the Hatay Metropolitan Municipality took place in November. A group of 20 young people, journalists and instructors from HATAY Mustafa Kemal University participated at the workshop, which was comprised by two sessions, the creative and the feedback session. During the creative phase, the participants made proposals on the design of the Hatay's pilot step.green page, while they provided their feedback as users of the STEP app.	24	11/11/2016
Workshop with the core team	Three workshops with the core team were organized by the Hatay pilot in order the STEP team to discuss the activities that will organize within the next months and collect young users' feedback on the STEP platform. A group of young environmentalists from Mustafa Kemal University in Hatay, who are also members of the NGO, "Genç Tema Vakfi" participated at the workshop.	7	04/01/2017 18/01/2017 01/02/2017
STEP Launch Event in Hatay	STEP's launch event was organized at the Municipality's Hall, which was full of University students, members of the Environment and Nature Association, City Council members, Young Municipality Employees, Hatay Media Center and Journalists' Society. The STEP project was presented and a	360	03/03/2017

	live demonstration of the platform followed. The agenda was also enhanced with additional speeches on important environmental issues that the Municipality will upload in the platform within the next months.		
National Sovereignty and Children's Day Celebration Festivals, Highlight to the life with bicycle, Hiking.	In order to celebrate these days the Municipality of Hatay with other stakeholders organized a bicycle tour. The Association of Environmental Volunteers, University Student Clubs, and the Hatay Bicycle Association Volunteers participated in the event. The Municipality of Hatay has uploaded a relevant dialogue in the STEP Platform, which was disseminated during this event.	~250	22 – 23/04/ 2017
Green Summit '17 " Conference in Istanbul University / Avclar Istanbul - Turkey	Hatay's STEP Team joined the conference, which was focused on the field of the environment. A number of discussions concerning Hatay's environmental issues took place with stakeholders, which helped STEP team to better understand the problems that are being discussed within the Municipality. As a result, a number of ideas for new activities and dialogues generated through this participation.	~400	25- 04- 2017
Opening of Water park	An info kiosk was set up during the Water Park Opening Festival in order to inform young people about the STEP project and the dialogues uploaded on the platform.	~2,500	29-30/ 04/2017
May Fest	This is a quite famous event in Hatay during which a number of parallel events take place. This year young people from Iskenderun and Hatay participated in the event, while University Students from Iskenderun Technical University & Mustafa Kemal University also attended it. An STEP info kiosk was set for the dissemination of the project. Additionally, during a famous Turkish singer, who gave a concert introduced the STEP platform and presented a new dialogue that was uploaded on the STEP platform.	~1,500	03-07/05/2017

Additional dissemination activities have been planned by the Municipality of Hatay for the upcoming months. By the end of October the Municipality will set up info kiosks in central and crowded places, such as the city center, shopping centers, Universities, etc. in order to disseminate more effectively the STEP platform to young citizens. Each kiosk will be equipped with one tablet and independent internet access. A representative of the STEP team will be at the kiosk, so as to demonstrate the platform, inform citizens about the new dialogues and support them during the process of e-participation.

5.4.2 *Communication with local stakeholders*

Hatay's communication with stakeholders proceeds according to the initial plan. More than 500 environmental youth community members became users of Step platform, while University Professors – Environmentalists support the STEP team and provide them with consultation.

Additionally, the Journalist Tuba Alvanoglu, who is also a panelist in Local Media for youth projects, has been working very actively in the dissemination of the STEP project.

5.5 Association of the Communities of Locride area

The Association of Communities of Locride area has developed a concrete dissemination plan for the promotion and of the STEP tool not only to young users, but also to policy makers. It should be noted that inspired from STEP, Sant'Agata del Bianco Municipality decided to amend town's Statute, so as young people above the age of 16 years to be able to participate in online petitions. STEP is considered valuable tool for maintaining relationships between administrators and young people. Apart from Sant'Agata, additional Municipalities expressed their interest for using the STEP solution in order to come closer to young people and involve them in decision making.

5.5.1 Dissemination Events

The dissemination activities of the Association of Communities of Locride area's pilot are briefly presented below.

Title of Activity	Brief description	Reach	Date
Presentation of the STEP project at the Municipality of Sant' Agata del Bianco	Students from 18 to 20 years old from "Marconi", a technical High School located in Siderno participated at the event. The participants were grouped in teams in order to discuss and exchange ideas on the topic of "Protection of green spaces in Siderno".	102	18/11/2016
Presentation of the STEP project at the Municipality of Sant'Agata del Bianco	Students from "Mazzini", a High School located in the city of Locri attended the presentation of the STEP platform. Additionally, the participants had the chance to share their opinion on e-democracy and e-participation topic, as well as to suggest the environmental issues they would like to be uploaded in the STEP platform.	130	30/11/2016
Workshop with the core team at Locri	Apart from the STEP team, 7 more stakeholders participated in this workshop in order to be informed about the STEP project and share their ideas on how to promote the STEP platform and what local environmental issues would attract the interest of young people.	7	03/02/2017
Workshop with the core team at Siderno	Apart from the STEP team, 15 more stakeholders (youth workers and students at the Technical Institute) participated in this workshop in order to be informed about the STEP project. The topic of waste collection was discussed and ideas on to improve day to day waste collection were put on the table.	15	13/02/2017

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<p>Info kiosk at Cosenza - Bbook Festival event</p>	<p>The Bbook Festival event(http://b-bookfestival.blogspot.it/) was a meeting among writers, authors, teachers, booksellers, associations and young students. Around 140 classes of local schools from Cosenza, Rende, Cirò, Corigliano, Fagnano, Paola, Cotronei, Marano, Mendicino, Reggio Calabria are invited to participate in this event. The purpose of the event is to bring the youth closer to the book sector and the stakeholders of this field.</p> <p>The STEP team participated in this event so as to introduce the platform to an audience of 20-35 years old, who are youth workers and can act as disseminators of the STEP concept.</p>	<p>~3,000</p>	<p>23/03/2017</p>
<p>Info kiosk at Catanzaro Event</p>	<p>The purpose of this event was to present a new initiative for the educational community in Calabria, called "The Challenge of the Educating Community in Calabria", which will deal with school dispersion, educational poverty, educational failure, as well as the worrying phenomenon of the Neet.</p> <p>The event attended the Minister of Public Education of Italy and the Regional Councilor for Education in Calabria, the Children's Guarantor of the Calabria Region, the director of the Regional School of Education Diego Bouchè, the national spokesman for the "Association network Crescere al Sud", the President of the Foundation for the School of Compagnia di San Paolo and the Italian-European director of Save the Children.</p> <p>A big number of participants and politicians visited the STEP stand and were informed about the project.</p>	<p>~450</p>	<p>30/03/2017</p>
<p>Introducing the STEP platform at school in Locri</p>	<p>The objective of this event was to meet young students and to discuss the benefits of e-participation. Additionally, the dialogues of the STEP platform were presented. During the event 6 groups of about 20 students were formed and interactive discussions on the dialogues of the STEP platform took place. The teachers also participated very active in the whole event.</p>	<p>120</p>	<p>March 2017</p>
<p>Launch of the Step Platform</p>	<p>The event was organized at the Municipality of Siderno. After the presentation of the project objectives and the platform, a session dedicated to the dialogues that will be uploaded on the STEP platform followed. Students, young people, environmentalists, as well as representatives and decision makers from various Municipalities joined the event. More specifically, the decision makers, who joined the event were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the Mayor of Sant'Agata del Bianco, - the Vice-Mayor of Siderno, who is also responsible of the Environmental Department, - the Chairman of the Association of the Municipalities of 	<p>70</p>	<p>11/05/2017</p>

	<p>Locride Area and Mayor of Benestare.</p> <p>During the event an official announcement took place concerning the amendment of the Statute of Sant'Agata's town. More specifically, Article 34 was amended, so as young people above the age of 16 years to be able to participate in online petitions. After the announcement, the decision-makers invited the students to participate in the dialogues uploaded on the Step platform and share their opinions on local environmental issues. All the mayors expressed their interest in using the Step platform as a tool to discuss about the environmental issue of their Municipalities with young people.</p>		
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Additional activities are planned to be implemented in the pilot area within the next months:

- Public conference at the University of Reggio Calabria – July 2017
- Youth STEP festival in Locride area – August 2017
- Public initiative with the youth associations of the Metropolitan city of Reggio Calabria –September 2017

5.5.2 *Communication with local stakeholders*

Common public initiatives (seminars and focus groups) were carried out by the Association of the Municipalities of Locride Area, and the Metropolitan city of Reggio Calabria in order to encourage youth to participate in public decision-making through the STEP platform.

A number of local Organisations and Institutions have actively supported the pilot and promoted the STEP platform. These are:

- the Association Civitas Solis
- the Environmental Association "Osservatorio Ambientale Diritto per la vita"
- the Environmental Association Federazione Mediterraneo Ambiente
- the Environmental Association, Aspromont Park
- the Technical State Institute "Guglielmo Marconi" Siderno
- the High School of Human and Linguistic Sciences / Liceum "G. Mazzini" Locri
- the Technical Vocational Training Institute IPSIA - Siderno - Locri

In June 2017, the "Aspromont Park" and the "Osservatorio Ambientale Diritto per la vita" will contribute in the launching of new dialogues in the STEP platform.

5.6 *Resilient Thessaloniki*

The additional pilot of Thessaloniki that joined STEP on its own accord rescheduled the local pilot plan, so as the first issue would be uploaded onto the STEP platform on May. This reschedule was due to the fact that Rockefeller Foundation selected Resilient Thessaloniki to be granted with the "Street Plans" services and the

Municipality decided to launch STEP to the citizens for this project. Street Plans is an award-winning urban planning, design, and research/advocacy firm with offices in America. This is a well-known firm for advancing innovative practices to test and implement projects on different topics including open streets and public space stewardship.

In this context, the launch event of the STEP platform took place on 8th of April during an interactive workshop with citizens and the representatives of the Street Plans. DRAXIS participated in the event and presented the STEP project and the platform, while the Resilient Thessaloniki and the Street Plans presented the Municipality's project about the open spaces in Thessaloniki. The first dialogue of Thessaloniki Municipality uploaded on the STEP platform at the end of May. Within the next months, Resilient Thessaloniki will organize additional activities for the presentation of the STEP tool.

6 Dissemination impact indicators

In order to qualify and evaluate the dissemination actions, STEP had set specific measurable goals. The implementation of the dissemination strategy was regularly evaluated according to the level of realisation of dissemination objectives and results set. The following table presents what had been achieved with respect to said targets. It should be noted that most of the targets initially set have been achieved. However, the partners should make extra effort in order to achieve the first three targets, which are the most difficult ones.

Indicator	Target Value	Achieved from June 2015 – May 2016	Achieved from June 2016 – May 2017	Target achieved so far	Source/ methodology
Number of visits to the project website	45,000	3,863	4,765 + 19,262 visits at the STEP platform	27,890	Google analytics
Number of followers in the social media accounts that will be opened	12,000	587	3,602	4,189	Accounts' data
Number of women followers in the social media accounts that will be opened	6,000	203	1,945	2,149	Accounts' data
Number of open events (clean-up/ restore events, thematic parades, food festival etc.)	6	-	23	23	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of participants in the open events (clean-	1,200	-	18,813	18,813	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination

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up/ restore events, thematic parades, food festival etc.)					activities within the project
Number of young participants in the open events (clean-up/ restore events, thematic parades, food festival etc.)	800	-	11,823	11,823	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of female participants in the open events (clean-up/ restore events, thematic parades, food festival etc.)	600	-	8,513	8,513	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of targeted events (workshops, roadshows)	12	0	22	22	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of young participants in the targeted events (workshops, roadshows)	500	-	614	614	Participants' lists
Number of female participants in the targeted events (workshops, roadshows)	300	-	479	479	Participants' lists
Number of non-project events where STEP project will be presented	6	15	31	46	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of entries (articles/ press releases) in local, regional and national press (printed and online)	30	16	26	42	Copies of the entries
Number of e-newsletters promoted	10	1	3	4	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project

Number of newsletters recipients	6,000	887	208	1,095	Mailing list record
Number of distributed printed material	4,000	1,526	32,800	34,326	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of viewers of project related audiovisual material	2,000	181	844	1,025	Number of views through YouTube
Number of stakeholders registered in the STEP network of interest	1,000	887	208	1,095	List of stakeholders
Number of scientific papers published	2	0	1	1	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project

7 Conclusions

This Dissemination Report provides a complete overview of the dissemination activities concluded in the scope of the STEP project from Month 13 until Month 24 in accordance with the provisions of the 2nd Dissemination Plan.

The main objective of the dissemination activities of this period was to widely disseminate the vision, concept, objectives and innovation of the project, as well as its intermediary results to commercial and general public communities. From the evaluation of these activities, it can be deduced that the performance of the STEP dissemination procedures is quite satisfactory and in accordance with the initial strategy. Most of the targets initially set have been achieved. However, project partners should make extra effort in order to reach dissemination targets; this is the reason why the 1st dissemination strategy was updated in M12.